

CASE STUDY: SITIA

This policy brief is an outcome of the NEVERMORE project. It was developed through a multi-step process that combined the characterization of the Sitia region, the definition of key policy storylines, expert consultations, and stakeholder surveys on implementation barriers and enablers. The effect of selected policies on key indicators was simulated using System Dynamics modelling, with an implementation period from 2030 to 2045 and two climate change scenarios (SSP2-4.5, an intermediate greenhouse gas emissions scenario, and SSP5-8.5, a very high greenhouse gas emissions scenario). Results from model simulations and the insights gathered throughout the process are the basis for the technical and policy recommendations presented in this brief.

Key Messages

Sitia is an extreme climate hotspot marked by thermal drought, strong winds and low rainfall, with increasing flash floods and coastal erosion. Climate risks threaten olive- and vine-based agriculture, water availability, biodiversity, and tourism. Adaptation to climate change is a priority, and risks can be reduced through education and training, urban planning, improved cropland management, and an integrated water policy (desalination, wastewater reuse and demand reduction). Mitigation complements adaptation through energy efficiency and uptake of renewables. Simpler procedures, local capacity, and better access to funding are crucial.

The Municipality of Sitia is located on the island of Crete, in Greece, and it belongs to the regional Department of Lasithi. Sitia is known as Europe's most "extreme climate hotspot" mainly because of thermal drought. Strong winds, almost 300 sunny days each year, and very little rain contribute to these extreme conditions. Several climate-related disasters have occurred over the past decade, including flash floods. In addition, coastal erosion threatens coastal habitats and human settlements.

Main economic sectors, challenges, and priorities

Agriculture: Sitia's economy has been traditionally based on agriculture, although production is sparse due to the stony and mountainous terrain. Tree crops, mainly olive groves, fruit trees and nuts, occupy the majority of agricultural land. The crops most affected by climate change are vines and olives, with expected large impacts on the economy of the area. The main challenges are related to temperature increase, droughts, higher intensity, and frequency of flooding phenomena and sea level rise.

Water: Prolonged drought conditions put pressure on freshwater availability, especially during summer when the demand from tourism and agriculture is high and expected to increase due to climate change. Existing water supply networks have leakage problems from ruptured pipes or blockages caused by the build-up of salt from brackish water.

Biodiversity: The Sitia UNESCO Global Geopark has several geomorphological peculiarities, with some unique habitats and ecosystems that are threatened by climate change.

Tourism: Another key economic activity is tourism, which is also affected by climate-related hazards (high temperature and floods) and water scarcity.

Priorities: All these aspects underscore the importance of policies aimed at reducing and managing climate-related risks, protecting people and key resources such as water and land, and ensuring the resilience of Sitia's economy. Preserving biodiversity, agricultural production, food culture, and archaeology are key priorities.

Decision-making and implementation context

Climate actions in Sitia are implemented by the municipality through local climate, energy, water, waste and civil protection planning, aligned with regional, national and EU frameworks. Governance involves consultative participation from universities, NGOs, private sector actors, and citizens. Policies span agriculture, water, energy and tourism, combining adaptation and mitigation measures. Monitoring relies on plan evaluations and stakeholder feedback, while funding remains insufficient and capacity-limited.

Technical and policy recommendations

1. Increase the capacity to adapt

The adaptive capacity of Sitia's population can be increased by providing education and training, while sensitivity can be minimized by improving green urban planning. A high implementation of such policies, supported by substantial incentives for education and training, can reduce climate-related risks for Sitia's population to zero even under the most adverse future climate scenario (SSP5-8.5). Maximum benefits can be obtained by providing education and training to at least 50% of the population and implementing green urban areas on at least 2.5 km² in the region. Considering that insufficient and complex funding mechanisms may constrain the implementation of extensive adaptation policies, technical support from regional authorities, development agencies and research institutions should be provided, while reducing administrative complexity.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Flood defences in urban areas	Yes	Yes	Yes
Green urban planning (km ²)	1	2.5	4
Education and training (% of population)	20	50	80

Risk index for Sitia's population (0-1) under two climate scenarios (SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5) for baseline and policy scenarios. It is calculated accounting for the probability of heatwaves, the exposed population, and their sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Dmnl=dimensionless

2. Protect agricultural production through improved cropland and water management

Sitia's agricultural production can be preserved by diversifying the production, increasing water availability and use efficiency, as well as investing in crop adaptation. Increasing water storage in agricultural land is key to facing water scarcity in the municipality, although the area available for crop production would be reduced. Crop diversification and increased water availability can reduce crops sensitivity to climate hazards, with the best results obtained with a high level of policy implementation, i.e. more than 50% of crop diversification and increased water use efficiency. At the same time, substantial incentives are needed to promote crops adaptive capacity, representing the main driver for improved cropland management, together with tailored guidance and information. Administrative complexity should be reduced while providing institutional support to land managers.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Investments in crop adaptation (million €)	10	50	100
Crop diversification (% of cropland)	20	50	80
Efficient water demand from agriculture (% reduction)	20	50	80
Water storage increase (Hm ³)	10	30	50

Crops sensitivity to climate change in Sitia for baseline and policy scenarios under a) SSP2-4.5 and b) SSP5-8.5 climate scenarios. Dmnl=dimensionless

3. Sustainable use of water resources

Water scarcity in Sitia can be contrasted by a comprehensive integrated water policy, aimed at increasing water availability as well as reducing water demand from different sectors. Ambitious water policies to reduce water demand from the agricultural, industrial and urban sectors by 80% and the increase in water supply through desalination and wastewater treatment, can ensure water security under different climate scenarios. The implementation of such policies, however, is constrained by the lack of infrastructure and institutional support and requires cross-sectoral coordination and coherence.

Water security is represented by a binary index equal to 0 when water supply is insufficient to meet demand and equal to 1 when supply fully satisfies demand. Baseline and policy scenarios were simulated under a) SSP2-4.5 and b) SSP5-8.5 climate scenarios. Dmnl=dimensionless

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Efficient water demand from agriculture, industry and urban areas (% reduction in demand)	20	50	80
Water storage increase (Hm ³)	10	30	50
Desalination increase (Hm ³)	10	30	50
Water treatment increase (Hm ³)	10	30	50

4. A resilient and diversified tourism sector

Tourism in Sitia can increase its capacity to cope with climate-related hazards, while also increasing its sustainability, by deseasonalizing tourist flows and investing in infrastructure. The risk index for tourism increases with the exposure to climate hazards; spreading tourist flows throughout the year and investing in adaptation and resilience not only can reduce risks but also increase revenues. Policies that promote resilient infrastructure with sustained investments can counteract the decline in tourist capacity, while a sustainable use of water resources should be prioritised to avoid aggravating water scarcity in the region. Availability and access to infrastructure and technology is indeed the main driver to a resilient and diversified tourism sector in Sitia, although institutional and financial support should also be granted.

5. A more efficient use of energy for climate change mitigation and adaptation

Climate change adaptation and mitigation go hand in hand, so that improving resource use efficiency can both increase resilience and reduce emissions. Increasing energy efficiency by 30% can substantially reduce energy consumption in Sitia, supporting a transformative transition to renewables. Such policies would enable drastic reductions in CO₂ emissions from the energy sector, with zero emissions in the high implementation scenario. At the same time, a lower demand for energy and phasing out oil as an energy source would be beneficial in terms of self-sufficiency and resilience, which is crucial in times of high instability.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Energy efficiency (% increase)	10	100	200
Energy transition model	Gradual	100	200
Incentives for energy efficiency and lower emissions	Low	1	2

Total energy consumption (million MVh) in Murcia for baseline and policy scenarios under a) SSP2-4.5 and b) SSP5-8.5 climate scenarios.

6. A pathway to decarbonization

Although climate change adaptation is the priority for Sitia's public authorities, mitigation actions are nonetheless urgent. A switch to clean energy, increasing solar (including on rooftops), wind and hydrogen capacity while reducing non-renewables would contribute to a low-carbon future as well as increasing total energy production in Sitia. Indeed, a high implementation of renewable energy policies would reverse the declining trend observed with the baseline and lower ambition scenarios. An ambitious energy policy would be in line with Crete's Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP), which aims to maximise the penetration of renewables in the insular energy system.

Total energy production (MWh) in Sitia under baseline and policy scenarios.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Solar capacity increase (MWh _y)	50	100	200
Wind capacity increase (MWh)	50	100	200
Solar production on rooftops increase (MWh)	0.5	1	2
Reduction in non-renewables production (MWh)	50	100	150
Incentives for renewables and carbon tax	Low	Medium	High

Conclusions:

Priority is adaptation: secure water, protect crops and biodiversity, and make tourism and settlements resilient to heat, floods and erosion, while cutting emissions via efficiency and renewables. Delivery requires cross-sector coordination, reduced administrative complexity, and sustained technical/financial support so municipalities can implement and access EU and regional funding.

CATALOGUE & LOCAL TOOL

Discover the NEVERMORE Catalogue of adaptation and mitigation policies and check the Local Tool to simulate the effect of more policy scenarios

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